

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE WAYS OF WORDFORMATION IN THE ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6545288>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st May 2022

Accepted: 10th May 2022

Online: 14th May 2022

KEY WORDS

language, comparing, classifying, word building, morphemic ways, composition, components.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses a comparative analysis of similar and the most productive ways of word formation processes in the English and Karakalpak languages. As a result, it hopes to emerge and serve as a subsequent and reliable, albeit partial, reference material for English and Karakalpak linguistics, particularly in terms of linguistic structures. The framework presented here for the study and analysis of word-formation processes in both languages may be used in future research.

The language we speak is one of the characteristics that distinguishes humans from non-human creatures. The need to identify the world language groups prompted the study of how languages differ in structure. This was started by linguists who studied history or comparative linguistics. Their goal was to show how similar they were. Even if languages are genetically distinct, several comparative studies have revealed that they may share similarities.

The linguistic system of each language is distinct. This system has numerous branches, each with its own set of sub-branches. Typology is one of these branches, and there are numerous types. Morphological typology is one of the most common categories. It's a system for classifying the world's languages. It divides languages into groups based on their morphological structures.

The interior structures of words are the focus of morphology. It investigates word

structures, particularly the tiniest linguistic units (morphemes). Morphology includes the process of word formation. It is concerned with the creation of new words and the relationships that result from them. It also looks at how old forms of words be repurposed while keeping or gaining new meanings.

The study of word building in English and Karakalpak is crucial since it aids in learning, understanding, and mastering the foreign language. As J.B.Buranov states, "The theoretical meaning of the comparative study is in its typological analysis and in the analysis of structural peculiarities of each comparing language . The practical significance of the comparative study is its using in the studying process " [1]. The question of the study of ways of wordformation in the Karakalpak language has its own history and there are various opinions concerning this issue. In 1950-1960-s appeared many works of the famous scholars in lexicology

of the Karakalpak language. The famous linguist N.A.Baskakov distinguishes three main ways of wordformation. They are: lexical, morphological and syntactical [2]. A.Kidirbaev distinguishes only two ways of wordformation in the Karakalpak language: morphological and syntactical.

Much attention to the questions of wordformation in the Karakalpak language began to be paid especially in the 1970-s. In the latest books devoted to the morphology of the Karakalpak language «Хәзирги қарақалпақ тили. Морфология» (Ноқис, 1981), «Хәзирги қарақалпақ әдебий тилиниң грамматикасы» (Ноқис, 1994), there are the following ways of wordformation in modern Karakalpak:

- 1) morphological;
- 2) morphological-syntactical;
- 3) lexical-semantic; and
- 4) phonetic-semantic.

The Karakalpak language has some common features with English in dividing all the derivative words according to their structure and form into two large groups: 1) morphemic way and 2) non-morphemic way. Morphemic way is one of the productive ways and it plays a great role in enriching the language vocabulary with new words. As we have seen above the most widely-spread morphemic way is affixation. Morphemic way is divided into the following groups: 1) Affixation; 2) Word composition; 3) Word composition and affixation and 4) Abbreviation.

Affixation is the formation of words with the help of derivational affixes. The process of affixation consists in coining a new word by adding an affix to the stem of a word. It is necessary to consider certain facts about the main types of affixes in Karakalpak. Words which consist of a root

and an affix (or several affixes) are called derived words or derivatives and are produced by the process of word-building known as affixation (or derivation).

In English all the affixes are divided into suffixes and prefixes, in Karakalpak affixation is divided into suffixation and postfixation. In suffixation an affix is added to the stem and other word-forming morphemes of the word. For example: *азат- азат-лық, бил- бил-им, дийқан- дийқан-шылық; өн-им-дар-лық, ас-паз-лық, қурал-сыз-лан-ды-рыў.* In postfixation an affix is added not to the stem or root of the word, but to word-forming morphemes only. This way is used widely in the formation of adjectives and adverbs in Karakalpak. For example: *мәртлерше - мәрт (түбир морфема,- лер (сөз өзгертиўши),- ше (рәўиш жасаўшы морфема); ойымша- ой-ым-ша; аўылдағы- аўыл-да-ғы.*

In Karakalpak as well as in English according to the parts of speech all the affixes are divided into noun-forming, verb-forming, adjective-forming and adverb-forming. There are two groups of affixes forming nouns in the Karakalpak language: nominative and verbal nouns. Nominative nouns are formed with the help of the following affixes: *-шы/ши, суўшы, падашы, теримши, балықшы - дас/ дес жолдас, қарындас, күндес, қурдас; -шылық/ ишлик, жүүеришилик, дийханшылық, егиншилик, саўдашылық; -лық-лик: темиршилик, балықшылық, фермершилик, туўысқанлық, балалық; -хана- жатақхана, шайхана, асхана;* Verbal nouns are formed with the help of the affixes: *- стан,-кер / гер, кеш / -ман / бан, -зар, -нама, -зада, -зат,* and others .

In English there are the following adjective-forming suffixes: *-able / ible, al, ian, -ese,*

ate, ed, ful, ive, ous, y; For example: *Italian Chinese, beautiful, communicative, famous – ate,-en, ify, ize*. In Karakalpak nominative adjectives are formed with the help of the following suffixes: *-лы/ли: тәртинли, саўатлы, атақлы, керекли; -сыз/ сиз: мазасыз, ҳәлсиз, менсиз; -дай/ дей, -тай /тей: айнадай, жақсыдай, ойымдағыдай –ғы-ги қы ки: жазғы, қысқы, бәхәрги, түски*.

Derivative verbs are formed from nouns, adjectives and adverbs with the help of affixes. If in English we use such verb-forming affixes as: *ate,-en, ify, ize. (communicate, broaden, modify, realize, organize)* in the Karakalpak language we use the following verb-forming affixes: */ле: даўыслы, гүрриңле, дузла, емле, тарбияла; -лас /лес: техникаласыў, активлесуў, газлесуў*. The other verb-forming suffixes are: *-ар/ер-р, ық-иқ, ғар/гер, қар-кер, сы / син, сын /син, шы / ши – қы / ки ай /ей*.

Thus, we see that in modern Karakalpak the morphemic way of wordformation coincides with the affixation in English and it is one of the widely-spread basic and the most productive ways of wordformation.

Word composition is one of the most productive methods of wordformation in

modern Karakalpak, as it involves merging two or more stems to create new words.

Compound words and word combinations are not the same thing. Compound words are one part of speech, whereas word combinations are made up of different parts of speech. For example: *бес-атар (қоспа сөз)-бес китап (анықлаўыш+баслаўыш); урын-сөгип (қоспа сөз)-сөгип сойледу*

(пысықлаўыш+баянлаўыш)

In English as we know compounds are divided into three types: 1) neutral; 2) morphological and 3) syntactical [5]. In Karakalpak compound words are divided into different types according to their form, types of components and degree of connection:

- a) constituent words (составлы сөзлер)
- b) pair words (жүп сөзлер)
- c) reduplicated (reiterated) words (тәкирап сөзлер)
- d) blending (бириккен сөзлер)
- e) shortened words (қысқарған сөзлер).

In conclusion, according to the study and analysis of different ways of word formation in two languages we see that both affixation and word composition are considered the most productive ways of word formation in both languages: English and Karakalpak.

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